

RACIALIZED XENOPHOBIA : IMPLICATIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF FORCED DISPLACEMENT

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7706884

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ABSTRACT

The present work focuses on two aspects: forced displacement as a type of contemporary migration in Brazil, and the implications of what, within the scope of this reflection, we call racialized xenophobia. Forced migration is commonly related to situations such as: economic crises, wars, ethnic-racial conflicts, epidemics and natural disasters. It is assumed that such situations added to the structural racism present since the genesis of Brazilian sociability present themselves as obstacles to the integration of a certain group of forced displaced people who, due to their ethnic-racial and cultural characteristics, are targets of racism and xenophobia.

Keywords: Forced displacement. Xenophobia. Racism.

1. INTRODUCTION

According to a report on poverty and human rights released in 2017 by the Inter-American Organization for Human Rights (OAS), people living in poverty are more vulnerable to trafficking for the purpose of labor and/or sexual exploitation. Also according to the same report, indigenous and Afro-descendant peoples who are discriminated against on racial, ethnic and social grounds, and who also live in situations of poverty, are more subject to such situations.

It is argued that the circumstances mentioned above, added to structural racism, result in the exposure of this population to a situation of vulnerability and social risk, leading a significant number of people to move in search of better living conditions.

Upon arriving at their destination, forced migrants are faced with a reality that is

characterized by several obstacles to their social insertion, marked by intense labor exploitation, structural unemployment, precarious work, above all, for certain groups that, due to material conditions, origin and ethnic-racial characteristics are discriminated against.

Given the above, it is intended, albeit briefly, to discuss the effects related to the intersection between racism and xenophobia in the context of forced displacement, as well as the implications for assimilation or discrimination of this population in their destinations.

2. RACIALIZED XENOPHOBIA AND FORCED DISPLACEMENT

Threat and scarcity at the origin, tragedies and invisibility on the crossing, inhospitality and exclusion on arrival, this is the saga that characterizes the trajectory of thousands of forced displaced people. This scenario is an expression of a contemporary world marked by a “perverse globalization” (SANTOS, 2006), in which we live a paradox: on the one hand, a dizzying mobility of capital, for which there are no borders and so little nationality, on the other hand, an intense restriction on human mobility, in an unprecedented context with regard to the prohibition of the movement of people (VENTURA, 2014).

There is, therefore, an evident contradiction within the scope of so-called globalization, because while the circulation of goods and merchandise is prioritized, the migratory flow is seen with distrust and threatens security, especially when it comes to migrants from the so-called global south towards the countries of central capitalism, notably the United States and Europe.

In this way, it is worth highlighting the contribution of Amin (2021), who, when problematizing Eurocentrism, refers to “anti-universalist-universalism”, which, based on the racialization of the human, conceives the white man as a universal being (essence of the human being).), and on the other hand animalizes the non-white, interdicting their recognition. Such differentiation serves as a justification for denying the rights of those considered “non-human”, including the right to move and/or settle in certain territories.

A current example of tensions between migration and racial issues can be seen in the effects of the war in Ukraine, which brings to light the contradictions of European migration policy, which is increasingly based on the racist distinction between "good" and "bad" migrants. Recently, right-wing Liberal candidate in France Valérie Pécresse expressed this judgment eloquently when she claimed that war refugees of Ukrainian origin should be encouraged to settle in the country, while others, largely Africans, should be invited to " return to their

countries" ⁵.

However, it is observed that xenophobic and racist manifestations aimed at forced migrants are not exclusive to countries of the so-called global north. In a survey ⁶organized by the NGO I am a Refugee with the Qualibest Institute in 2021, five hundred and three (503) people were interviewed, including refugees and asylum seekers in Brazil. In the total of that sample, 47% of the interviewees said they had suffered some type of discrimination in the country, especially related to nationality and race. Among African refugees, the percentage is much higher: 64%.

This finding reveals a paradox, since according to data released by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE) 54% of the Brazilian population is black. In this regard, it is worth mentioning the contribution of Frantz Fanon who, when dealing with the misadventures of the national conscience, observes that the colonial logic, in addition to creating a racialized hierarchy based on the supposedly universalizing Eurocentrism, contributes to the emergence of racist and xenophobic manifestations within the former colonies, which, by assimilating this culture based on estrangement from the other, create an atmosphere of hostility and violence between different groups (ethnic, religious, etc.) on the continental and national levels.

In this way, the manifestations of racism and xenophobia within many countries of the African continent and in Latin America are examples of colonial influence in post-colonialism, stimulating the creation of an ultranationalism in countries whose constitution of their sociability was based on diversity. and coexistence of distinct groups, (FANON, 1961).

The western bourgeoisie has built enough barriers and bridges not to really fear competition from those it exploits and despises. Western bourgeois racism with regard to the Negro and the *bicot* is a racism of contempt; it is a racism that minimizes. But bourgeois ideology, which proclaims an essential equality among men, manages to remain in line with itself, inviting sub-men to humanize themselves through the type of Western humanity that it incarnates. (FANON, 1961, p. 9)

Furthermore, it is known that since the colonial period, the development of the productive forces in the central economies, occurs from the plundering and expropriation of the

⁵ War in Ukraine reveals tensions between demography, migration and race. Available at <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/colunas/mathias-alencastro/2022/03/guerra-na-ucrania-revela-tensoes-entre-demografia-migracao-e-questao-racial.shtml?utm_source=whatsapp&origin=sheet>

⁶Refugees consider Brazilians welcoming, but suffer discrimination, says research. Available at <https://www1.folha.uol.com.br/mundo/2022/03/refugiados-consideram-brasileiros-acolhedores-mas-sofrem-discriminacao-diz-Pesquisa.shtml?utm_source=whatsapp&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=compwa>

colonies and dismantling other forms of sociability, undermining the possibilities of development in the explored territories. About this it is worth mentioning:

The settler's city is a satiated, indolent city, whose belly is permanently filled with good things. The colonist's city is a city of whites, of foreigners. The city of the colonized, or at least the indigenous city, the black city, the medina, the reserve, is a place of ill repute, populated by men of ill repute. There you are born no matter where, no matter how. "You die no matter where, no matter what" (FANON, 1961, p. 26)

The scenario described above by Fanon gains greater clarity and breadth in his perception with the impressive advances in New Information and Communication Technologies (NTIC) that shorten distances and reduce time, feeding the imagination of those who live on the periphery of the world and who envision the possibility of leaving the "disreputable" places towards the "satiated" and "indolent" cities.

However, forced displaced people, especially those who are racially displaced, when arriving at their destination face several barriers: unknown language, lack of support from the public authorities, abusive exploitation of work, hunger, difficulty in finding housing, criminalization, intimidation and threat of expulsion, xenophobia and racism

This scenario contradicts what is advocated by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, proclaimed in 1948 by the United Nations (UN) and ratified by Brazil in 1968, which considers Human Rights, such as the right to life, freedom, work, health, education, among others, inherent to all people, regardless of their nationality, race, gender, ethnicity, language or religion.

3. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

By revisiting the processes that lead a significant portion of the population to forcibly move, and the social meaning attributed to racialized migrants, the scope of this work sought to discuss the implications of the intersection between xenophobia and racism.

It is worth questioning the adequacy of regulatory frameworks and the effectiveness of migration policies, with regard to the difficulties of integrating certain groups and social segments due to their ethnic-racial characteristics.

In other words, in addition to issues related to *status* and/or migration modalities, it is important to consider in the set of normative frameworks aspects related to ethnic-racial tensions that constitute obstacles to the integration of certain groups.

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